

RISK ACCEPTANCE CRITERIA FOR RAILWAY SYSTEMS

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Abstract

The development of modern railway systems, such as high speed railway systems or railway lines with extremely long tunnels, requires the assessment of the safety level of the planned railway system and the verification of its acceptability. However, technical standards or codes for railway systems do not include risk acceptability criteria but only qualitative safety provisions.

This paper addresses the definition of target safety levels for railway systems: first acceptability criteria for other industrial activities such as air transportation, offshore or chemical plant operation, etc., are reviewed, secondly a methodology to define specific acceptability criteria for railway systems is discussed and applied to define target safety levels for the societal risk applicable in Western Europe.

1.0 Introduction

The railway is moving now rapidly toward a modern service transportation industry. High Speed Rail (HSR) systems are already operating in Japan, England, France, Italy and Germany. A further development of the whole European HSR network is planned. The design velocity is of the order of 250 Km/h and, to be guaranteed, a considerable part of the routes is in tunnels with lengths greater than 10 kilometers and in four cases of the order of 50 kilometers.

In this European context, the Commission of the European Communities has published a report (Commission des Communautés Européennes, 1990) aimed at homogenizing the HSR projects and safety issues are also addressed. This report will form the basis for a unified European code for HSR systems to be issued in 1993.

However, neither this CEC report nor existing railway regulations and codes directly address the problem of quantitatively assessing the safety level for railway systems. This is mostly due to the fact that railway transport is considered by railway operators, and perceived by the public, as a safe mean of transportation. This approach to safety might be applicable to traditional railway systems which have proven throughout the years their performance; it is however not enough to guarantee the safety of railway systems where innovative and particular conditions are present, or of existing lines that have to be upgraded to new exercise standards.

For example, the combination of:

- o high speed transit;
- o combined transport of passengers and dangerous goods;
- o extremely long tunnels;

might lead to unacceptable safety levels, and therefore the designer has to choose a railway system configuration together with preventive and mitigative measures of accidents that minimize the risk and ultimately, should verify by means of a risk analysis that the obtained safety level is below a predefined target level.

This paper addresses the problem of defining such a target safety level. A brief review of the acceptability criteria adopted in other industrial activities is first provided, then a methodology to define specific acceptability criteria for railway systems is presented and is then applied on data recorded on western Europe railways to define a target safety level for the societal risk.

2.0 Generalities on Risk Acceptability Criteria

Risk for an industrial activity is generally associated to events that might cause damaging consequences on people (sanitary risk) or to events that might cause system downtime (economic risk). Only sanitary risk is addressed in this paper. Sanitary risk can also be distinguished into risk for a single person (individual risk) and for the collectivity (societal risk). The individual risk expresses the probability that a person suffers consequences of a given accidental event not taking into account the number of persons present where the accident occurs. On the other hand, collective risk is a function of the number of people involved and of their possibility to move away from the site of the accident.

The acceptable individual risk is also a function of the individual's involvement; different acceptable levels should be defined for activities where the individual voluntarily exposes himself to the hazard with respect to an involuntary participation (see for example Fritzsche, 1988). For voluntary risk it has been defined a upper limit of probability of death per year equal to 10^{-2} ; while for the involuntary risk the following values have been suggested:

$p > 10^{-4}$	not acceptable;
$10^{-6} < p < 10^{-4}$	tolerable;
$p < 10^{-6}$	acceptable.

For societal risk, the acceptability criteria is based on the definition of an acceptable probability range for events of given consequences. Of course, to the severest consequences are associated the lowest values of the acceptable probability.

3.0 Safety Standards for Other Industrial Activities

A brief review is provided of the acceptability risk criteria proposed or adopted by different industrial sectors. Table 1 summarizes the type of approach followed by these industries to define safety targets.

Road Transport

Road accidents have been extensively analyzed and several statistical synthesis have been presented. Nevertheless, roadway regulations do not present any quantitative evaluation of the present risk level for the roadway system and do not propose acceptable limits on the occurrence of accidental events.

Air Transport

Risk acceptability criteria have been defined for the air transport by some rules and regulations, however, no unique criterium exists yet. At present one can consider that the acceptable risk level is 10^{-7} accidents per hour of flight, corresponding to approximately 2×10^{-10} accidents per kilometer of flight.

Chemical Industry

Chemical industries are exposed to hazards which may cause fires, explosions, toxic releases; risk analyses in the chemical industry has therefore a strong tradition. Figure 1 (from Van Kuijen, 1989) present quantitative criteria for the definition of societal acceptable risk levels. These criteria are however considered strict and are currently under discussion.

Nuclear Power Plants

Safety is obviously a major concern for nuclear power plants. During design, anomalies with a probability of occurrence lower than 10^{-6} per year are disregarded. Several studies performed for some plants concluded that the probability of core fusion is of the order of 10^{-4} - 10^{-5} occurrences per year.

Offshore Production Platforms

Several studies have addressed the definition of target safety levels for societal risk for the offshore industry. The Department of Energy (DOE), for example, has quantified its recommendations as exemplified in Figure 2. The Norwegian Maritime Directorate (NMD) has estimated a target annual probability for accidental events of 10^{-4} , corresponding to a return period of 10,000 years. In Canada it have been defined safety criteria, based on cost/benefit considerations and comparison to other industrial risks (Jordan, 1988), that indicate an annual probability of 10^{-5} for catastrophic consequences, 10^{-3} for severe consequences and 10^{-1} for minor consequences.

Table 1: Risk Acceptability Criteria for Various Industrial Activities

CRITERIUM INDUSTRY	QUALITATIVE	SEMI QUANTITATIVE	QUANTITATIVE
Road Transport	X	X	
Air Transport		X	
Chemical		X	
Nuclear			X
Offshore			X

4.0 Methodological Aspects

The basic criteria for the definition of a target safety level for a railway system is that of assuming that the safety inherent in the traditional railways in the last two or three decades is acceptable. The safety target is therefore derived by analyzing the railway recent risk history in terms of frequency of occurrence of accidents and extent of their consequences.

The procedure generally used to estimate the risk associated to railway transport is based on the analysis of the frequency of occurrence of given consequences for a given accident; risk R_i for the i -th type of accident is therefore given by:

$$R_i \approx p_i C_i \quad (1)$$

where:

p_i = probability of occurrence of the i -th type of accident;
 C_i = expected consequences of the i -th type of accident.

Globally, the generic risk R_t is defined as:

$$R_t = \sum_i p_i C_i \quad (2)$$

Consequences C_i are generally classified according to three levels of gravity: "medium", "severe" and "catastrophic". To each of these classes it has been associated a mean number of victims:

- o medium consequences: 3 victims;
- o severe consequences: 30 victims;
- o catastrophic consequences: 300 victims.

The evaluation of the probability p_i can be performed by assuming that accidental events occur according to a Poisson process, this means that accidental events are independent (Benjamin and Cornell, 1970).

The probability of having n accidental events of type i during the time T is given by:

$$p_i (n|T) = \frac{e^{-\mu T} (\mu T)^n}{n!} \quad (3)$$

where μ is the frequency of occurrence of the accidental events; while the probability of having at least one accidental event n_0 in the same time is given by:

$$p_i (n_0|T) = 1 - e^{-\mu T} \quad (4)$$

For accidents associated to catastrophic consequences only a few events occurred and therefore statistical data are not sufficient to provide reliable estimates. For these events it is therefore recommended to use a bayesian approach (Benjamin, 1968).

The probability of having at least one accident during the time T_0 , having observed n events in a time interval T , is given by:

$$p [n_0 | T_0, n, T] = 1 - \frac{1}{\left[1 + \frac{T_0}{T}\right]^{n+1}} \quad (5)$$

5.0 Recommended Risk Acceptance Criteria

For individual risk, a target safety level that has been proposed and accepted is an annual probability of fatality of 5×10^{-5} (derived from Bohnenblust and Schneider, 1984). However, to reach an individual probability of being involved in a fatal accident of 5×10^{-5} , it would require such a high number of kilometers per year to be extremely unlikely.

For societal risk the methodology of Chapter 3.0 has been applied on data of recorded accidents of the italian, austrian and german railways. Results are presented in Figure 3 in a diagram where the consequences, in terms of expected victims, are plotted against the annual probability of having at least one accident that leads to these consequences. Results are considered valid for a first definition of an acceptable safety level for Western Europe railway systems.

The following can be observed in Figure 3:

- o to events of medium consequences it is associated a annual probability of 10^{-9} (per train-kilometers);

- o to events of severe consequences it is associated an annual probability of 10^{-10} (per train-kilometer);
- o to events of catastrophic consequences it is associated a probability of 10^{-11} (per train-kilometer).

The curve of Figure 3, therefore defines the acceptability conditions for the studied railway systems, in particular p-C conditions that fall below the curve are associated to acceptable safety levels.

Supposing, for example, that to a tunnel of approximately 50 kilometers length is associated a daily traffic of 200 trains in both directions, the return periods associated to the accidental events are:

- o medium consequences: 100 years;
- o severe consequences: 1,000 years;
- o catastrophic consequences: 10,000 years.

The return period for "medium consequences" would then result of the same order of magnitude of the mean life of important infrastructures, such as for example a HSR line or a long alpine tunnel.

For catastrophic consequences, the return period results of the same order of magnitude of that accepted, for example, for offshore production platforms and chemical plants (of the order of 10,000 years) while it results lower than the limit imposed for nuclear plants, which are however associated to consequences of significantly higher gravity.

As a final remark, it should be noted that the p-C curve proposed in Figure 3 represents the mean outcome of a probabilistic analysis where several random variables, associated to various uncertainties, have been considered. The acceptability of points falling close to the curve should therefore be critically evaluated.

Ultimately, further studies should be aimed at defining not just an acceptability curve, but a "desired" region in the p-C diagram which takes also into due account cost-benefit considerations.

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FIGURE 1: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PROBABILITY CAPABILITY OF THE INSTALLATION AND SEVERITY OF EFFECTS FOR OFFSHORE INSTALLATION (DOE, 1989)

FIGURE 2: SOCIETAL RISK ACCEPTANCE CRITERIUM FOR THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY (VAN KUIJEN, 1989)

FIGURE 3: RISK ACCEPTANCE CRITERIUM FOR RAILWAY SYSTEMS